

Constrained Dynamics Simulation: More With Less

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I. INTRODUCTION

Efficient robot dynamics simulation is a fundamental problem key for robot control, identification, design and analysis. Efficient simulation is a crucial enabler of model predictive control (MPC) [54] and learning-based control [44], arguably two of the most successful and currently the most actively researched advanced robot control techniques. It can improve the optimality and safety properties of MPC by enabling a longer prediction horizon [54], enabling highly dynamic robot behaviour¹ close to system limits. Efficient simulation can shorten training times of learning-based controllers, such as a reinforcement learning (RL) [62, 9] based controller, where the learning phase often relies heavily on simulation [44] due to the prohibitive cost and safety concerns involved with training on real robots. Faster and physically accurate simulators can democratize robotics research by potentially not requiring dedicated expensive resources like high-end GPUs and physical robots for training and validating controllers. Accurate simulation is also key to task and motion planning (TAMP) [67, 31] that will be essential for intelligent robots executing long-horizon tasks robustly. Finally, simulation profoundly impacts several adjacent fields like biomechanics [20] and computer graphics [18].

Current simulator efficiency is insufficient. Simulation is often the bottleneck, particularly in MPC, where evaluating dynamics and derivatives can take up to 80% of the total computation cost [5]. Consequently, achieving whole-body MPC for high degree of freedom (DoF) systems like humanoids remains an open problem. Moreover, industrial applications of solving minimum-time optimal control problems with full dynamics models, to maximize economic objectives like bin picks-per-hour [56], is also limited perhaps due to the long solution times [34] offsetting the performance gains. Moreover, simulation inefficiencies force roboticists to ignore submechanisms like gears [37] or joint flexibility [4], which causes significant simulation errors [17]. Inspired by the large language models’ (LLMs) [3, 68] success, early works have trained large multimodal models targeting robotics [21, 11]. Simulation is attractive [23] for generating sufficient amount of diverse data for training these data-hungry models. Considering the scale of the typical datasets [11], reducing the carbon footprint of generating training data and evaluating trained models in simulation, assumes key importance.

Drawbacks of existing simulators. Solving the inner equality constrained dynamics problem [28] is often the most computationally expensive aspect of simulating contact dynam-

ics. To solve these inner problems, most existing simulators (RBDL [29], RAISIM [35], MUJoCo [66, 65], PINOCCHIO [14], DRAKE [64], DART [43], BULLET [18] and PhysX² to name a few) use Featherstone’s branching-induced sparsity-exploiting LTL algorithm [26, 27], which however has an expensive computational complexity of $O(nd^2 + m^2d + dm^2 + m^3)$, where n , d and m are the robot’s DoF, kinematic tree’s depth, and constraint dimensionality respectively. This worst-case cubic complexity renders the LTL algorithm inefficient for high DoF robots. Other recent simulators like BRAX [30] adopt a computationally even-worse approach of Gauss-Seidel iterations to solve the KKT system arising from the inefficient [28] maximal coordinate formulation of Baraff [7]. But they mitigate their algorithmic inefficiency to an extent by exploiting the compute power of GPUs or TPUs. However, there exist more efficient recursive algorithms [53, 70, 6, 51] in dynamics literature that have been forgotten or ignored that have linear complexity in n .

These low-complexity recursive algorithms offer a unique and untapped opportunity to accelerate existing simulators. However, they require a revival and possibly an improvement. The low-complexity algorithms require non-trivial extensions to efficiently support closed-loop mechanisms. An efficient C++ implementation is also essential to fully exploit an efficient algorithm. A simulator for robotics should be physically realistic and not ignore complementarity constraints [65] or linearize the nonlinear complementarity problem [18] (NCP) associated with the frictional contact problem, as this realism can potentially require less domain randomization or control feedback to deal with simulator error. Finally, the simulator should also be differentiable with smoothing [60] without sacrificing efficiency to enable trajectory optimization and learning for contact-rich tasks. None of the existing simulators satisfy all the requirements listed in this paragraph and building one is my current research problem.

II. CURRENT RESEARCH

Linear complexity constrained dynamics algorithms: I derived a family of efficient constrained dynamics algorithms (CDAs) [57] for kinematic trees by solving an equivalent discrete-time linear quadratic regulator (LQR) problem [54], arising from Gauss’ principle of least constraint [32, 69, 12]. I first revisited and revived the efficient, but largely unknown, Popov-Vereshchagin (PV) CDA [53, 70] from 1970s, with a complexity of $O(n + m^2d + m^3)$. Since the original paper [70] has no derivation, I provided an expository derivation

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tf4DML7FIWk>

²<https://developer.nvidia.com/physx-sdk>

in [57] by adapting the textbook dynamic programming [8] approach to solve the corresponding LQR problem [54]. I further extended the PV algorithm to floating-base trees, with constraints permitted on any link, and updated it with modern efficiency techniques discovered over the years like adding uniform gravity field [10], using local frames [10] and using DH nodes [48]. Then, by exploring LQR solver variants, I proposed two new CDAs [57] with asymptotically optimal $O(n + m)$ complexity, namely PV-soft and PV-early, derived using MUJOCO-style relaxed constraints and aggressive early elimination of Lagrange multipliers respectively. My numerical results indicate significant simulation speed-up of 2x for high dimensional robots like quadrupeds and humanoids.

The LQR/optimization connection in my derivation makes CDAs accessible to researchers with control and optimization background, which includes many roboticists due to the popularity of OCP solvers [63, 24, 47], who currently use CDAs as a black-box. This connection facilitated my follow-up work [55] on proximal [52] dynamics algorithms three original dynamics algorithms, the most efficient among which is constrainedABA with $O(n + m)$ complexity. These proximal algorithms relax the constraint linear independence assumption in the PV solvers, are numerically robust to singular cases, automatically return least-squares solution for even infeasible motion constraints [16, 33]. They generalize existing algorithms, namely PV-soft and the CDAs in MUJOCO and DRAKE allowing trading-off compliance and rigidity in contact through proximal iterations. ConstrainedABA is particularly simple and easily implemented requiring only a few additional lines of code compared to Featherstone’s articulated-body algorithm [25, 28], facilitating its implementation in existing simulators.

Lowest complexity Delassus matrix algorithms: The Delassus matrix [19, 22] or the inverse operational space inertia matrix (OSIM) [40] is key to efficiently differentiating [14, 50] CDAs and solving frictional contact problems [22, 36, 45]. I discovered that the PV algorithm computes the Delassus matrix as an intermediate quantity, thereby providing a new Delassus matrix algorithm (PV-OSIM), with a computational complexity of $O(n + m^2d + m^2)$. I further accelerated PV-OSIM for floating-base robots with branching at the base using the matrix inversion lemma [59]. PV-OSIM was found to be significantly faster for most realistic robots (upto 2x for humanoids) than the existing state-of-the-art recursive algorithms, KJR [41] and EFPA [71], which have a complexity of $O(n + m^2d + m^2)$ and $O(n + md + m^2)$. In a follow-up work [58], I exploited the compositionality of the extended force and motion propagators [46, 15] in PV-OSIM computation to obtain the PV-OSIMr algorithm, with an optimal complexity of $O(n + m^2)$. However, computing constraint forces requires factorizing the Delassus matrix, which incurs an additional $O(m^3)$ operations for all the above algorithms. The combination of proximal algorithms and the matrix inversion lemma in my recent work [55], yields a new algorithm cABA-OSIM, that can compute even the damped Delassus inverse matrix in just $O(n + m^2)$ operations. cABA-

OSIM was found to be over $3x$ faster for humanoids than the widely-used Featherstone’s LTL-OSIM algorithm [27, 14].

Implementation: All the low-complexity dynamics algorithms mentioned above have been recently implemented in C++ within the high-quality open-source dynamics library PINOCCHIO [14] and will shortly be released to the community. PINOCCHIO was chosen because its efficient implementation alone provides several times speed-up compared to other simulators [18, 43] also written in C++.

III. FUTURE RESEARCH

Short term: There exist several pressing extensions and clear short-term future research directions. Mechanisms with **internal closed-loops** [38] are inadequately addressed in most existing simulators and recent robot designs increasingly use internal loops [2, 1] for mechanical reasons. We have made initial progress on extending the proximal dynamics algorithms [55] to closed-loop mechanisms. Next, these low-complexity algorithms will be used to solve **inequality constraints** and **frictional contact problems**, thereby delivering a fully-fledged efficient simulator using our low-complexity algorithms. The lessons learned in [45] will be used to ensure the physical realism of the frictional contact simulator.

Making our low-complexity simulator **differentiable** is the natural next step. I expect the derivative computation to be significantly accelerated due to my cABA-OSIM algorithm and through a C++ implementation by adopting the implicit function approach [13]. Note that using proximal algorithms makes differentiation through our proximal CDAs well-defined (over finite number of iterations) even for singular/infeasible cases due to the differentiability of the proximal operator. To obtain informative gradients despite the non-smoothness inherent in frictional contact problems, I plan to explore and support the randomized smoothing methods [61, 60, 42] with our low-complexity algorithms.

Medium and long term: In the medium and long-term, my work will explore applications and opportunities enabled by the fast and differentiable simulator. Armed with the cumulative speed-ups we expect due to algorithmic improvements as well as efficient implementation, a medium-term direction is to push towards **whole-body MPC** for humanoid-sized robots. For long term, leveraging the gradient information from the simulator to reduce the **sample complexity of RL** or imitation learning, where the current models and learning methods remain data-hungry [39], is another potentially interesting direction. This can be critical for manipulation tasks where there is arguably a higher diversity of challenges compared to the locomotion tasks, making data generation challenging. Finally, another exciting longer term direction is enabling **long-horizon planning** [49] for set of tasks requiring fast and dynamic tool use [67] using physically realistic simulators.

Finally, through efficient algorithms and implementations, I hope to democratize robotics research by enabling prototyping and deployment of advanced control techniques like MPC and RL even on resource-constrained computational platforms.

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